

“INVESTORS’ PERCEPTION TOWARDS EXCHANGE TRADED FUNDS (ETFs), THEIR POPULARITY AND ADVANTAGES: A STUDY WITH RESPECT TO BENGALURU URBAN”

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Abstract

The Indian ETF industry has grown from 6 ETFs in 2007 to 66 in 2018 at 28% CAGR over a 11 year period. AUMs grew 10x in the last three years from Rs. 8900 crores to 89,500 crores as of October 2018 over a period of 3 years. Government of India is using the easier ETF route to raise money as a part of disinvestment strategy (Aruna Polisetty, et al., 2019). CPSE ETF a flagship product launched in March 2014 was oversubscribed and excess Rs. 1363 crores was refunded as the issue size was limited to Rs. 3000 crores. The very introduction of new ETF categories - Debt ETF and smart Beta ETFs or ETF 2.0 are picking up trade and this speaks about financial market is joining the matured market league.

Purpose: The purpose of the study is to highlight the factors driving perceptions of respondents towards investment, analyse the reasons behind popularity of ETFs. The various advantages of ETFs are also studied in detail. The study intends that ETFs can be more popularised through investors camps, simplified products, lower tax treatment which further encourage more investors to try ETFs.

Design / approach: A structured closed ended questionnaire was administered as schedule in order to avoid delay, non-response and the fear of Covid-19 pandemic. A total of 115 questionnaires were in the hand and out of 115 only 100 are usable one forming 86.95% success rate. Chi-square, contingency co-efficient, ANOVA, Garrett ranking technique and weighted average statistical tools were performed for the present study analysis.

Findings: All the socio-economic characteristics showed significant relation with ETFs investment and the contingency coefficient reveals high degree of relationship between socio-economic characteristics and investments in ETFs. Investors perception towards ETF investment are measured and presented by using weighted average technique. Future prospects, multiplication of money and wealth creation, are the investors perception which are ranked respectively on the basis of strength of WA. The study also reveals about reasons behind the popularity of ETFs and they include increased demand for low cost products like ETF, cost efficiency, convenience of exchange trading and transparency. The study also reveals about advantages of ETFs wherein these advantages are measured by applying Garrett Ranking Technique.

Implications: The study will be useful to the investors and policy makers. There exist strong relationship between the socio-economic characteristics and investments in ETFs. The study reveals high degree of relationship between the characteristics and investments in ETFs. The buoyancy in demand enhanced when the government of India selected the ETF route for disinvestment. However, through proper conduct of investors meet, simplification of products, lower tax treatment and lower expenses would encourage more investors to invest in ETFs.

Keywords: ETF, smart beta, physical gold, publicity, reasons, advantages, convenience.

Introduction

ETF is an innovative financial product that connects mutual funds and stock. ETF as a mutual fund provides benefits to the investors as risk can be reduced by making investment in a diversified portfolio and ETFs as a stock can be bought and sold in stock market throughout the day. They are wonderful product innovation in the last 25 years. The Toronto 35 Index participation Fund (TIP 35), launched in 1990 in Canada, is perhaps the first ETF (Aruna Polisetty et al., 2019). The first US ETF S&P SPDR (Spy / spiders) launched in 1993. The global ETF industry is managing \$4.9 trillion Assets under Management (AUM). US leads ETF volume with a 72% market share followed by Europe 16%, Asia Pacific 9% and the rest of the world 3%. The first Indian Nifty Benchmark Exchange Traded Scheme (NIFTY Be ES) was launched in 2001 by Benchmark Mutual Funds. At present in India Motilal Oswal NASDAQ 100 ETF is the best to buy as it is giving 2 year return 39.54% pa. It is projected by the end

of 2022 the best India ETFs are SMIN, EPI, and GLIN with the best one year trailing. There are over 7600 ETFs at global level representing about 7.75 trillion US dollars in assets. The exchange traded funds in India crossed a new milestone as there are now 100 ETFs listed on National Stock Exchange. ETFs are the safest way of investing money in trades. ETFs are popular and attractive investments because of their low cost and stock like features (Yasmeen Bano and Vasantha 2017). The investment in gold requires huge investment which made impossible for the small and marginal investors to invest in gold with the emergence of gold ETFs many of the disadvantages with other modes of investment in gold has been overridden. Gold ETFs are the funds which closely follow the price of physical gold. They are the units representing the units of physical gold and can be in paper form (Yadav et al. 2018). ETFs are the most tax efficient because of their in kind creation and redemption process, which allows for arbitrage and pricing efficiency. In the case of ETFs only the transacting shareholder is taxed, while the gains are shared by all shareholders. But in case of mutual funds the tax is shared by one and all unit holders.

Statement of the problem

Investors are said to be rational and wealth maximizes. The investors like to multiply wealth and care about their future. Some investors like to create wealth and also wants tax saving. The investor follow basic financial norms on the risk return considerations as the driving factor of investment decision making (Baker et al., 1977). The rational investors are driven by multiple number of consideration before they invest. Investors are contended with expected return and firms financial stability and these are important investment drivers (Baker et al. 1973). The recent financial crisis reveals the significance of identifying the factors influencing the investment behaviour. The behavioural finance theory states that a deep understanding of behavioural psychology of investors deeply gives insight into stock market anomalies and investment strategy selection. Understanding of investors psychology is more important and raising up of capital is highly decided by the investors psychology. A better understanding of the investors psychology in investment decision making helps the investors to convert their behavioural biases into benefits which motivates them to invest further.

The introduction of ETFs is to enhance the liquidity of the portfolio of a retail investor of late ETFs are preferred form of parking investment by retail investors. The price of the gold ETF is determined by the underlying asset held in the form of gold (Sathish Kumar et al., 2019). Further, to popularise the ETFs there is every need of conducting investors meet to create awareness, tax reduction and simplification, so that new set of investors may to opt t invest on ETFs.

Reveiw of literature

Velumurugan, P.S. et al., (2013) conducted a comparative study in gold related assets with an objective to examine the performance of gold related instruments namely, Gold ETF, Gold mutual fund and physical gold and also ascertain the better investment among the return of gold ETFs and gold mutual fund. The result reveals that there is a significant difference among the Gold ETFs, Gold mutual funds and physical gold. The study proved empirically that making investment in gold related assets like Gold ETFs are more profitable compared to invest in Gold Mutual Fund investment.

Saleem and Khan (2013) tried to trace the emergence and history of Gold ETFs in India and also to explain proper working mechanism of this fund along with portfolio risk diversification and tax implementation of Gold ETFs fund in India. Their comparative study of gold and gold ETFs reveals that gold ETFs are very attractive investment destination due to low price, smaller denomination and other advantages over physical gold.

Goyal, M.M., (2014) in their study between 2007-2014 they have revealed Gold ETFs are providing higher average returns at a lower risk as compare to the market. Further the researcher has stated that systematic risk for the Gold ETFs are negative implying that inclusion of gold stocks in the investors portfolio will make it more diversified and riskless.

Srinivasulu Sunkara et al. (2017) found in their study that majority of people are interested to grow their money but are hesitant to invest in securities of greater risk but provides better yield. All the respondents are aware of shares and mutual funds provide quick and higher returns but they are hesitating to take risk.

Sailaja Vedala et al. (2018) concluded in her study that ETF funds are known by people but they do not know the importance of them. The investment decision depends upon the factors like age, risk taking capacity and the return for their investment and there is significant relationship between personal attributes and investor perception except in the case of educational qualification and knowledge.

Arun Polisetty et al. (2019) stated in their research that penetration of ETFs is low in India due to lack of product understanding and lengthy and uncomfortable transaction process. Further, the researchers have expressed that Indians are still largely comfortable with traditional savings products over investing and within the investing universe, active fund management dominates passive. The authors suggested that investor camps, simplified products, lower tax treatment would encourage more investors to try ETFs.

Nishmita Ahuja (2020) found in their research that majority of the people are interested to grow their money but are hesitant to invest in securities which carries greater risk but provides better yield. A large number of respondents said about investment for future. All the respondents are well aware that shares and mutual funds provide quick and higher returns, but they are not confident to take risk. The researcher concluded just by stating that risk has a major impact on the investing decision of investors.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the socio-economic characteristics of respondents.
2. To analyse investors perception behind investment.
3. To study reasons behind popularity of ETFs.
4. To study advantages of ETFs.

Hypotheses

1. The socio-economic characteristics of responds are not impacting on the study.
2. Investors do not possess perception towards investment.
3. There are no reasons for popularity of ETFs.
4. There are no advantages of ETFs.

Research questions

1. Why the characteristics of respondents are not impacting on the ETFs investment?
2. What are the perceptions behind ETFs investment?
3. What are the reasons behind popularity of ETFs ?
4. What are the advantages of ETFs ?

Limitations of the study

1. The study is confined only to Urban Bengaluru.
2. Meeting the respondents was a little difficult on account of lack of time for the working respondents.
3. Covid-19 and Omicron third wave made little difficult to collect the necessary information.

Research Methodology

The paper aims at evaluating the perception of respondents for investing in ETFs in India. The paper also aims at studying of reasons behind popularity of ETFs and advantages of ETFs. The present study is based on both primary and secondary data. A questionnaire was prepared to know about gender, marital status, age, education, occupation, monthly income, type of family preferred level of risk, investment vehicle, behaviour towards ETFs and source of information. Based on the answers data has been collected and analysed.

Research design, Source of data and data collection: Questionnaire was administered as schedule to collect the primary source of data. The structured questionnaire contained closed ended questions. The secondary sources include journals, books, articles. Data has been compiled from these sources in order to improve the understanding of the topic and to be able to analyse the data collected. Due to the nature of research topic it was decided to adopt survey method.

Sample size and sampling technique : Convenient sampling technique was used to collect the data. It is a non-probability sampling technique where subjects are selected because of their convenient accessibility and proximity to the researcher. The sample size was determined as 100 due to covid-19

pandemic and to follow the Covid rules and regulations. The type of sample respondents include salaried employees, business community, self employed, startup entrepreneurs homemakers and retired persons.

Data collection tools : The data collected was tabulated properly. In order to analyse the data the study uses Chi-square, contingency co-efficient, ANOVA, weighted average and Garrett Ranking Technique. These techniques are used since they are simple, understandable and sufficient for the study's objectives.

Scope of the study : The present study is only confined to Urban Bengaluru. The selected areas were Gandhinagar, corporation, Jayanagar, Rajajinagar, Malleshwaram. The study covers the significance of investing in ETFs which are becoming popular now-a-days. They are very simple for transaction, low cost and most demanded. ETFs are becoming most lucrative and important tool for investing and the purpose of this study is to make them popular as they are less risks and safety investment. These characteristics include marital status, gender, age, education, occupation, monthly income, type of family, preferred level of risk, investment vehicle, behaviour towards ETFs, guiding factor for investment and source of information.

Data presentation and analysis : Demographic profile of respondents - A

Research question No. 1 : What are the reasons behind the socio-economic factors are not impacting on the investment?

Hypotheses : No. 1 : H0 : The socio-economic characteristics are not impacting on the investment.

H1 : There exist significant variation in the socio-economic characteristics of respondents.

Table - 1 reveals data about respondents socio-economic characteristics. There are 80 males and 20 females and 83 respondents are married and 17 remained single. 38 respondents belong to the age group of 41-50 years, 25 to the group of 51-60 years, 15 to the more than 61 years, 12 to the 31-40 years and 10 to the 25-30 years group. There are 35 respondents who are getting monthly income in between 60K - 80K, 25 earning in the range of 80K - 100K, 20 to the 40K - 60K, 8 < 20K, 7 in between 20K - 40K and finally 5 respondents earning > 100K per month. As far as education is concerned 45 respondents are general degree holders, 20 are post graduates, 15 professional degree holders like doctors, advocates, chartered accountants and engineers, 12 completed PUC and 8 studied up to 10th standard. The occupation details reveals that 38 are salaried respondents, 25 doing business, 19 retired persons, 10 homemakers 5 self employed and 3 were start up entrepreneurs. There 75 joint families and 25 nuclear families. 60 respondents wants safety of investment without risk, 25 ready to take up medium risk and 15 ready to take high risk. The investment advisors include 69 authorised brokers, 21 friends and relatives and 10 robo advisors. The investment vehicle details reveals that 32 liked ETFs, 18 mutual funds, 13 fixed annuities 11 individual stocks, 8 individual bonds, 7 variable annuities, 6 hedge funds and 5 mutual fund wrap programs. The behaviour towards ETFs reveals that 53 stated good behaviour, 37 medium and 10 low. The source of information includes 56 stock brokers 22 friends, 15 financial advisors and 7 newspapers. All the socio-economic characteristics are significantly impacting and there exists high degree of relation between independent and dependent variables.

Research Question No. 2: What are the perceptions behind ETFs investment?

Hypotheses No. 2: H0: There is no significant variation in the investors' perception behind ETFs investment.

H1: There exist significant variation in the data and investors do possess perceptions behind ETFs investments.

Table - 2 depicts data about investors' perceptions behind ETFs investments. These perceptions vary from wealth creation, tax savings and future prospects to wealth creation, multiplication of money and future prospects. The respondents are shown in the form of Likert scale with scale points strongly agree to strongly disagree. The weights are given which are depending upon the scale points and hence we have scale points 1 to 5. The sum of all frequencies is 100 equals to sample. The respondents were asked to express multiple options about their perception towards investment. Weights are multiplied by respondents' opinions to get fw (frequency multiplied by weight). The sum of fw(frequency multiplied by weight) is divided by the sum of weights i.e., $(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) = 15$ to get weighted average. Further, the ranks are awarded based on the strength of WA i.e., sum of $(f \times w)$ horizontal

line to know the relative importance of WA rank wise. Accordingly, the first rank was assigned to future prospects, the second rank relative important was multiplication of money and third to the wealth creation and future prospects. The remaining ranks were awarded on the strength of WA. The final rank was awarded to wealth creation, multiplication of money and future prospects.

Research question No. 3: What are the reasons behind popularity of ETFs?

Hypotheses No. 3: H₀: There exist no significant variation in the reasons behind popularity of ETFs.

H₁: There exists significant variation in the data and there are reasons behind popularity of ETFs.

Table - 3 depicts data about reasons for popularity of ETFs. These popularity reasons are measured and presented in the table which varies from raising investors awareness among high-net-worth individuals to dip in actively managed funds. 62 respondents out of 100 expressed strongly agree followed by 24 agree and 14 somewhat agree. Out of 62 respondents who said strongly agree 15 spoke about increased demand for low-cost products like ETFs, 11 expressed about cost efficiency, 8 pointed at convenience of exchange trading, 7 said about transparency, 6 each revealed about transact @ intraday levels, and raising investors awareness, 5 spoke about dip in actively managed funds and 4 noticed about diversification. Out of 24 who said agree, 6 each spoke about cost efficiency and increased demand for low-cost products like ETFs, 3 expressed about transact @ intraday level. Out of 14 who stated somewhat agree, 3 each said about low-cost products demand and cost efficiency. ANOVA fails to accept H₀ and accepts H₁ and hence it is concluded that there exists significant variation in the data and there are different reasons behind popularity of ETFs investment.

Research Question No. 4: What are the advantages of ETFs?

Hypotheses No. 4: H₀: There exist no significant variation in the advantages of ETFs.

H₁: There exist significant variation in the advantages of ETFs.

Table - 4 reveals data about advantages of ETFs. These advantages vary from easy transactions to open trading. To measure the advantages and to rank the advantages Garrett Ranking Technique is adopted. Calculated values are computed by using the formula $100(R_{ij} - 0.5) / N_j$ and the computed values are referred to the Garrett ranking conversion table (Table-5). The scale and value x is depending upon the number of factors. The frequencies are multiplied by the value x derived by referring the calculated values to the Garrett ranking conversion table. Depending upon the strength of mean score the ranks are awarded. Accordingly, first rank is awarded to safe asset, the second rank to the secure investment and the third rank was awarded to easy transaction. Similarly, the remaining factors was ranked depending upon the strength of the mean score.

It was found on the basis of respondents' opinion that socio-economic characteristics are impacting very much the investments. Investors perception towards investment reveals that the respondents preferred future prospects, multiplication of money and wealth creation, future prospects. Further the respondents revealed about the advantages of ETFs which include increased demand for low-cost products like ETFs, cost efficiency, convenience of exchange trading and transparency.

Summary and discussion of findings

The main objective of the present study is to know how far the socio-economic characteristics impact on the investment. Further the study also analyses the investors perception behind investment, reasons behind popularity of ETFs and also analysis the advantages of ETFs. The study is made more pertinent by referring and considering experts and scholars contribution in the similar line of area.

In order to make a study on perceptions of respondents towards investments, analyse the reasons behind popularity of ETFs and to analyse the advantages of ETFs, survey research design was adopted. A structured closed ended questionnaire was administered as schedule after considering the issued like to avoid delay non-response and respecting 3rd wave pandemic norms to follow. The target population covered respondents of Bengaluru Urban. The type of participants includes salaried, business community, self-employed, start-up entrepreneurs, home makers and retired persons. The findings of the study reveals that the socio-economic characteristics are supporting and impacting on investments. The study reveals about investors perception about investment. The investors perception was measured by performing weighted average technique and relative important factors are ranked on the basis of strength of WA. The study found that investors are driven by future prospects and it was awarded first rank, the second rank was awarded to multiplication of money and the think rank was awarded to

wealth creation, future prospects. The study revealed about the reasons behind popularity of ETFs. They include increased demand for low-cost products like ETFs, cost efficiency, convenience of exchange trading and transparency. Further, the study also reveals about the advantages of ETFs. The ranked advantages reveals that the first rank was given to safe asset, the second rank to secure investment and the third rank was awarded to easy transactions. To analyse the above advantages Garrett ranking technique was performed. The study reveals about the presence of significant socio-economic characteristics and all the characteristics reveal high degree of relationship.

It was found on the basis of respondents' opinion that socio-economic characteristics are very much impacting on the investments. Investors perception towards investment reveals that they preferred future prospects, multiplication of money and wealth creation, future prospects. The study also reveals about the advantages of ETFs. The ranked advantages reveal that safe asset, secure investment, and easy transactions. Further, the study found about reasons behind popularity of investments. They include increased demand for low-cost products, cost efficiency and convenience of exchange trading and transparency. The convenient sampling technique was performed at the time of data collection. However, the questionnaire was used to obtain the primary source of data and the secondary sources include e-journals, books and internet. The findings of the study were presented, analysed and discussed using simple percentage, chi-square, contingency co-efficient, weighted average, ANOVA, Garrett Ranking Techniques.

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Table - 1 : Socio-economic characteristics of respondents

Characteristics	χ^2	TV@0.05	df	result of χ^2	“c”	Result of ‘C’
Gender	36.00	3.841	1	Significant	0.51	High Degree
Marital Status	43.56	3.841	1	Significant	0.55	High Degree
Age in years	26.90	9.488	4	Significant	0.46	High Degree
Monthly income (INR)	43.26	11.070	5	Significant	0.55	High Degree
Education	42.90	9.488	4	Significant	0.55	High Degree
Occupation	53.81	11.070	5	Significant	0.59	High Degree
Type of family	25.00	3.841	1	Significant	0.44	High Degree
Preferred level of risk	33.50	5.991	2	Significant	0.50	High Degree
Investment advisors	59.06	5.991	2	Significant	0.60	High Degree
Investment vehicle	44.96	14.067	7	Significant	0.55	High Degree

Behaviour towards ETFs	28.34	5.991	2	Significant	0.46	High Degree
Source of information	55.76	7.815	3	Significant	0.60	High Degree

Source : Field Survey

Note : χ^2 = chi-square

'c' = $\sqrt{\chi^2 / (\chi^2 + N)}$

Where 'c' = contingency coefficient

N = Number of observations

When the value 'c' is equal or near 1, it means there is high degree of association between attributes. Contingency co-efficient will always be less than 1.

Table - 2: Investors Perception towards ETF investment

Factors	Weight Likert Scale	5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SDA	Total	WA
Wealth creation, tax savings and future prospects	f	72	18	6	2	2	100	V
	fw	360	72	18	4	2	456	30.40
Multiplication of money	f	79	15	2	2	2	100	II
	fw	395	60	6	4	2	467	31.33
Multiplication of money and future prospects	f	71	19	7	2	1	100	IV
	fw	355	76	21	4	1	457	30.47
Future prospects	f	81	14	2	1	2	100	VII
	fw	405	56	6	2	2	471	31.40
Wealth Creation	f	72	16	7	2	3	100	VII
	fw	360	64	21	4	3	452	30.13
Multiplication of money, tax savings	f	65	18	8	7	2	100	X
	fw	325	72	21	14	2	434	28.93
Tax savings, future prospects	f	74	15	5	3	3	100	VI
	fw	370	60	15	6	3	454	30.27
Wealth creation, future prospects	f	75	16	5	2	2	100	III
	fw	375	64	15	4	2	460	30.67
Wealth creation and tax savings	f	65	10	12	7	6	100	XIII
	fw	325	40	36	14	6	421	28.06
Tax savings	f	72	12	8	4	4	100	IX
	fw	360	48	24	8	4	444	29.60
Wealth creation, multiplication of money, tax savings	f	70	14	10	3	3	100	VIII
	fw	350	56	30	6	3	445	29.67
Wealth creation and multiplication of money	f	65	15	9	5	6	100	XI
	fw	325	60	27	10	6	428	28.53
Multiplication of money, tax savings and future prospects	f	64	16	8	6	6	100	XII
	fw	320	64	24	12	6	426	28.40
Wealth creation, multiplication of money and future prospects	f	61	15	9	8	7	100	XIV
	fw	305	60	27	16	7	415	27.67

Source: Faced Survey

Likert scale: SA - Strongly Agree, A - Agree, N - Neutral, DA - Disagree, SDA - Strongly Disagree

Weights: 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 = 15

Weighted average = Total / sum of weights

fw=frequencyXweight

Table - 3: Reasons behind popularity of ETFs

Different Reasons	SA	A	SWA	T
Raising investors awareness among high net worth individuals	6	2	1	9
Diversification	4	1	1	6
Cost efficiency	11	6	3	20
Convenience of exchange trading	8	2	1	11
Transact @ intraday levels	6	3	1	10
Transparency	7	2	2	11
Dip in actively managed funds	5	2	2	9
Increased demand for low-cost products like ETFs	15	6	3	24
Total	62	24	14	100

Source: Field Survey

Note: SA - Strongly Agree, A - Agree, SWA - Somewhat Agree, T - Total

Hypotheses

H_0	There exist no significant variation in the data	Reject
H_1	There exist significant variation in the data	Accept

ANOVA Table

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F-ratio	5% F limit (From F table)
Between the sample	160.3336	(3-1)=2	160.336/2 = 80.1668	80.1668/5.8571 = 13.6871	
Within the sample	123.000	(24-3)=21	123 / 21 = 5.8571		(2, 21) = 3.47
Total	283.3336	(24-1)=23			

Source: Survey Data

ANOVA Analysis: The calculated value being 13.6871 higher than the TV = 3.47 @ 5% level of significance with $df = v_1 = 2$ and $v_2 = 21$ fails to accept H_0 and accepts H_1 and hence it is concluded that there exist significant variation in the data.

Table - 4: Advantages of ETF's - Garrett Ranking Technique

Ranks	Scale & Score value of ranks											Total	Mean Rank Score	Rank
	Factors	Scale value(x)	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX			
Easy Transactions	f	32	21	15	8	6	5	4	4	3	2	100		
	fx	2624	1470	945	456	318	235	168	148	90	36	64.90	64.90	III
Inexpensive	f	35	20	13	9	5	4	4	2	4	4	100		
	fx	2870	1400	819	513	265	188	168	74	120	72	64.89	64.89	IV
Tax benefits	f	28	22	9	8	7	8	4	5	4	5	100		
	fx	2296	1540	567	456	371	376	168	185	120	90	61.69	61.69	VII
Secure investment	f	37	24	12	8	3	4	3	3	4	2	100		
	fx	3034	1680	756	456	159	188	126	111	120	36	66.66	66.66	II
Safe asset	f	34	25	15	9	3	3	4	4	2	1	100		
	fx	2788	1750	945	513	159	141	168	148	60	18	66.90	66.90	I
Hedge against inflation	f	30	16	11	6	8	8	7	4	5	5	100		
	fx	2460	1120	693	342	424	376	294	148	150	90	60.97	60.97	VIII
Simple trading	f	32	21	12	10	7	4	5	4	3	2	100		
	fx	2624	1470	756	570	371	188	210	148	90	36	64.63	64.63	V
Portfolio diversification	f	30	15	18	7	8	7	6	3	4	2	100		
	fx	2460	1050	1134	399	424	329	252	111	120	36	63.15	63.15	VI
Loan collateral	f	22	15	8	8	12	6	9	8	7	5	100		
	fx	1804	1050	504	456	636	282	378	296	210	90	57.06	57.06	IX
Open trading	f	23	11	10	6	8	10	12	8	7	5	100		
	fx	1886	770	630	342	424	470	504	296	210	90	56.22	56.22	X

Source: Field Survey

Note: X - scale value; f - number of respondents; R - Rank

Mean score = Total score / N

Table - 10: Garrett Ranking Conversion Table

Sl.No.	$100(R_{ij}-0.5)/N_j$	Calculated value	Garrett Value
1.	$100(1-0.5)/10$	5.00	82
2.	$100(2-0.5)/10$	15.00	70
3.	$100(3-0.5)/10$	25.00	63
4.	$100(4-0.5)/10$	35.00	57
5.	$100(5-0.5)/10$	45.00	53
6.	$100(6-0.5)/10$	55.00	47
7.	$100(7-0.5)/10$	65.00	42
8.	$100(8-0.5)/10$	75.00	37
9.	$100(9-0.5)/10$	85.00	30
10.	$100(10-0.5)/10$	95.00	18

Source: (1) Subhash Vadgule (2016). Village consumer behaviour towards perishable goods. A study with respect to Ahmednagar district of Maharashtra, Pezzottaite Journals, 5, (3) 2286-2287. (2) <https://pd4pro.com.edu>